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Role	Name	Organisation	Date	File suffix
Main author(s) / Task Leader(s)	Kim Stobberup and Karim Erzini	CCMAR	23/03/2022	KS, KE
Contributors/Reviewers	Benvindo Fonseca	IMAR I.P.	23/03/2022	BF
	Ghoufrane Derhy	UCA		GD
	Karima Khalil	UCA		KK
	Khalahi Brahim	IMROP		KB
	Khalid Elkalay	UCA		KEL
	Margarita Rincón	CSIC		MR
	Ndiaga Thiam	CRODT		NT
WP leader	Karim Erzini	CCMAR	23/03/2022	KE
Coordinator	Jónas R. Viðarsson	MATIS	30/03/2022	JRV
Administrative Coordinator	Oddur Már Gunnarsson	MATIS	30/03/2022	OMG

Deliverable D2.8

Report on biological and ecological data in FFDB

30/03/2022

Executive Summary

This is the third and final report on the FarFish data base (FFDB). Task 2.3 (Advancing biological and ecological knowledge) of WP2 in FarFish aims to compile and make available in the FFDB, developed in WP6, data for the relevant stocks in the different Case Studies (CS). The data feeds into models and management tools that provide better understanding of the biology and ecology of the respective species and ecosystems, and will be used by other WPs (1, 3, 4, 5 & 6) for stakeholder interaction, development of management recommendations (MRs), modelling, stock assessment and for visualisation tools.

The two previous reports (D2.3 and D2.6) provided an overview of the data that was obtained and used as example data sets for the implementation of the Data Limited Methods (DLM) package and as input to the other WPs. In this report we focus on other sources of data, especially data that we were not able to obtain, namely Nansen survey and national research surveys.

The report provides a comprehensive overview of Nansen surveys and national research survey for the CSs. It is clear that a plethora of data suitable for application of Data DLM exists, especially in the form of national pelagic and demersal research surveys that are more continuous than the Nansen surveys. Acquisition of Nansen data was hindered by bureaucratic procedures and we strongly recommend a revision of the Data Policy to facilitate access to data. We also recommend that Nansen surveys should take into consideration the requirements for assessment and management of CSs and regional fisheries; lack of continuous time series of sampling makes Nansen data of limited use for assessment and management purposes.

Reluctance on the part of CS national institutes to provide national survey data for the FFDB limited the implementation of DLM. However, some example data sets were used to illustrate the possibilities of DLM and it is hoped that CS participants will bring their own national research survey data to the FarFish DLM course organized by WP7 with the collaboration of WP6 (planned for October 2021). We strongly recommend that CS partners explore the use of national survey and fisheries biology data for assessment of data limited stocks.

The report also reviews data collected by Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement (SFPA) observers and data collected by observers within the Data Collection Framework (DCF). It was concluded that the SFPA-observer data is of limited use for scientific advice purposes, while DCF data was much more complete and detailed, and could be useful for scientific advice. The final section provides an overview of the data available in Regional Fisheries Management Organizations (RFMO) such as the International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic tunas (ICCAT) and the Indian Ocean Tuna Commission (IOTC).

Abbreviations

CCMAR	Centro de Ciências do Mar
CDCF	Centre for Development Cooperation in Fisheries (Norway)
CECAF	Fishery Committee for the Eastern Central Atlantic
CSIC	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (Spain)
CRODT	Centre de Recherches Océanographiques de Dakar-Thiaroye (Senegal)
CS	Case Study
DCF	Data Collection Framework
DG MARE	Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries
DLM	Data Limited Methods
EU	European Union
EU-MAP	EU Multi-Annual Programme
EAF	Ecosystem Approach to Fisheries
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
FAO	Fisheries and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations
FFDB	FarFish Data Base
FPA	Fisheries Partnership Agreement
IEO	Spanish Institute of Oceanography
IOTC	Indian Ocean Tuna Commission
IRD	Institut de recherche pour le développement (France)
JSC	Joint Scientific Committee
ICCAT	International Commission for the Conservation of Atlantic Tunas
IMROP	Institut Mauritanien de Recherche Océanographique et des Pêches
IMR	Institute of Marine Research (Norway)
INDP	Instituto Nacional de Desenvolvimento das Pescas (Republic of Cape Verde)
LW	Length-weight
MCS	Monitoring, Control and Surveillance
MS	Member State
NANSIS	Nansen Survey Information System
NORAD	Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation
RFB	Regional Fishery Body ⁵⁵
RFMO	Regional Fisheries Management Organization
RV	Research vessel
SFA	Seychelles Fishing Authority
SFPA	Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreement
TD	Tagging data
UCA	Université Cadi Ayyad (Morocco)
WP	Work Package

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1 Introduction

In the first two years of the FarFish project data lists of species for each Case study (CS) were drawn up, sources of data identified, contacts were made with RMFOs, DG MARE, and national institutes. Data compilation was largely driven by the FarFish Data Base (FFDB) template developed in WP6 (see deliverables [D6.1](#) and [D6.4](#)) and the need of other data, especially time series, for visualization purposes. Data was acquired from DG MARE, and time series of catches and CPUE and biological/fisheries parameters for some of the bycatch species selected for study were compiled (FarFish [D2.3](#) and [D2.6](#)).

Nevertheless, there was limited success in gaining access to other potentially useful sources of data including the EAF-Nansen programme surveys carried out in CS waters, regional fisheries management bodies such as CECAF, national institute survey data, and catch and effort and bycatch of the European Sustainable fisheries partnership agreements (SFPAs) fleets. The major reason for the inability to acquire the most relevant and important data for the purposes of FarFish (time series of catch and effort, size distributions) is the reluctance and/or ability of national institutes to provide this data to FarFish. Likewise, access to EAF-Nansen survey data was not possible due to its data policy and numerous bureaucratic obstacles.

Although it was not possible to obtain EAF-Nansen and CS national research survey time series, this did not have a significant impact on the ability of the project to deliver expected products or results. The data that was obtained was sufficient for demonstration of the FarFish-DLMtool and has been adequate for providing the necessary inputs to the other FarFish WPs. Furthermore, there is still the possibility of CS partners bringing their national research survey data to the coming FarFish DLM course.

This report contains an overview of some of the time series of data that are available from CS national demersal and pelagic surveys, Nansen surveys as well as other sources. It is hoped that this will serve as an incentive and a basis for the CS partners to apply data-limited approaches for stock assessment of by-catch and other species that are currently not assessed.

1 Scientific surveys

The following sections attempt to give an overview of scientific surveys carried out in FarFish CS countries. The initial focus is on the surveys of the RV Fridtjof Nansen which have played an emblematic role in exploring and investigating the fishery resources of many developing countries, and thus contributed to establishing baselines and ecosystem considerations. Using the Nansen surveys as starting points, a more general overview is given on existing survey data for the CS, although this should not be considered a complete picture. For example, numerous efforts involving exploratory fishing and smaller studies are not considered.

1.1 Surveys of the RV Fridtjof Nansen

The so-called Nansen programme has been operating for more than 40 years, providing support for coastal developing countries to assess and manage their fisheries.¹ The goals and objectives of the programme have evolved over time, responding to new global challenges and the needs of recipient countries.

FAO has been collaborating with the Norwegian Agency for Development Cooperation (Norad) and the Institute of Marine Research (IMR) of Bergen, Norway in the implementation of the various phases of the Nansen programme since its inception. Norad has been the owner of the three research vessels (RV) since the start in 1974.

There have been four main phases of the Nansen programme, as shown in Figure 1 (Groeneveld, J.C. & Koranteng, K.A., 2017)

Phase 1 (1975-1980): Exploratory surveys which were aimed at finding fish resources in the waters of newly independent states of the Indian Ocean, bordering on the Arabian Sea and adjacent Gulfs, Eastern Indian Ocean, and the Southwest Indian Ocean.

Phase 2 (1980-1990): Detailed mapping of resources within countries' EEZs which focused on detailed mapping and taking inventory of fish resources within the EEZs of beneficiary countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America.

Phase 3 (1990-2006): Monitoring, management and capacity development which expanded on the original scope of the programme by including capacity building in fisheries research and management (institutional strengthening in partner countries). Regional collaboration and transboundary issues became central in the delivery. Emphasis was placed on countries and institutions in South Western Africa as well as Northwest Africa and the Gulf of Guinea.

¹ <http://www.fao.org/in-action/eaf-nansen/en/>

Phase 4 (2006-2017): Furthering the implementation of the Ecosystem Approach to Fisheries (EAF). During this phase, the programme was managed directly by FAO and worked in close collaboration with Large Marine Ecosystem projects and other projects around Africa.

Figure 1. Areas covered during the four phases of the Nansen Programme (1975–2016)

The programme attempts to address the following main challenges:

- Inadequate knowledge of the impacts of stressors such as fisheries, climate variability and change, pollution on marine ecosystems and their social and economic consequences,
- Inadequate systems and practices for sustainable management of marine capture fisheries, further challenged by climate and pollution impacts, and
- Insufficient capacity for implementing EAF, including for the promotion of gender equality and effective participation of women.

1.2 Nansen data availability, storage and ownership

Since 1980s, fishing data has been managed systematically and distributed to the users by means of an integrated data management and analysis software, which was specifically designed for this purpose.² This dataset comprises the main managed data from the EAF-Nansen program.

² http://preface.imr.no/index.php/EAF_Nansen_Data_Service

In addition to the immediate transfer of raw data files collected during a survey to its participants, a copy of the same data is stored at IMR for permanent storage. Designed for pure backup purposes, the database comprises all unmanaged data categories collected with RV Dr. Fridtjof Nansen since 1975. This repository is maintained at The Centre for Development Cooperation in Fisheries (CDCF), a department of the IMR.

The policy concerning the data collected by the surveys in the framework of the Nansen Programme is that these are owned by the developing country, which hosts a specific survey or, in the case of transboundary surveys, are shared by such neighbouring countries. As the transboundary surveys constitute a large proportion of the total survey effort, the bulk of the historically collected data has a shared ownership.

According to the above data policy, access to data in the repository is restricted to their owners and those users who are authorized by them.

1.3 The Seychelles: Mascarene Region

The first RV Nansen (active between 1975 and 1993) surveyed in the Western Indian Ocean between 1975 and 1990, visiting the Seychelles in 1978 (Groeneveld, J.C. & Koranteng, K.A., 2017). Thereafter there was a 17-year gap before the second RV Nansen (active between 1994 and 2016) returned to the region in 2007, including a survey covering the Seychelles in 2008, as shown in Figure 2 (Groeneveld, J.C. & Koranteng, K.A., 2017).

The Mozambique subregion was surveyed most frequently (14 times) and over the broadest time period (1977–1990 and 2007–2014). Other subregions were surveyed only once, or a few times over four decades, thus providing point estimates, but not time-series information.

No specialised software was used to capture, or store data collected by the first Nansen during the early years of surveys, and much of the data were stored in hard copy only. From the late 1980s, data were stored onto the Nansis database (Nansen Survey Information System).

Two research vessels were used over the review period. The first RV Dr Fridtjof Nansen was active in the Western Indian Ocean between 1975 and 1990. It was replaced by a larger and more modern Nansen in 1994, although this vessel first surveyed the Western Indian Ocean in 2007.

Figure 2. Survey areas: 1 = Somali Coast; 2 = East Africa Coastal Current; 3 = Mozambique; 4 = Madagascar and Comoros; 5 = Mascarene; 6 = Seamounts.

The first Nansen survey in the Mascarene subregion around Seychelles was in 1978 and 30 years before this subregion was revisited by the second vessel. The second set of surveys covered a much larger part of the Mascarene Plateau, including around Mauritius (2008 and 2010), the northern part of the subregion stretching southwards from Seychelles in 2008, and the southern part of it stretching northwards from Mauritius in 2010, as shown in Figure 3 (Groeneveld, J.C. & Koranteng, K.A., 2017).

The 1978 survey investigated the distribution, abundance and biology of commercially important fish stocks on the Mahé Plateau, whereas later surveys had a broader focus and multidisciplinary approach. Surveys after 2007 studied the hydrographic characteristics of the Mascarene Plateau, and the productivity, biodiversity and biomass of the pelagic ecosystem.

Figure 3. Sampling stations in the Mascarene subregion

Various methods and gears were used in the surveys covering the Seychelles. In 1978, this included an acoustic survey which found pelagic fish (*Decapterus sp.*) scattered over most of the main bank. Note that this concerns coastal fish resources, but this does not capture more oceanic species such as tunas and other large pelagics. A few trawls were undertaken around Seychelles in 1978, as shown in Figure 4, mainly because of uneven bottom topography and/or corals (Groeneveld, J.C. & Koranteng, K.A.m 2017). As an alternative to bottom trawling, some surveys have focussed on the feasibility of demersal fish traps, line fishing, and acoustic assessment of deeper (100–350 m) demersal fishes (Figure 4).

Although not precise, this method provides information on distribution and relative density of fish, particularly at night, when fish rise from the bottom to feed. High spatial variability in fish density is observed, with the highest relative densities associated with the bank’s edges (especially the eastern edge), because productivity is higher along the edges than over the central bank.

Figure 4. Distribution of demersal fish on the Seychelles Bank based on acoustic recordings in 2008

More recently, in 2018, the RV Fridtjof Nansen has carried out a so-called Ecosystem Survey of East Africa, including the Seychelles and Mascarene region³.

- Ecosystem Survey East Africa - Leg 1; Period: 20/01/2018 - 03/05/2018; Countries: Mauritius - Seychelles - Sri Lanka
- Mascarene Bank Survey - Leg 2; Period: 04/05/2018 - 22/06/2018; Countries: Mauritius - Seychelles - Sri Lanka

This survey off East Africa had a broad ecosystem approach and aimed at gaining understanding of the ecosystem status in general, and of specific ecosystem components and attributes in particular.

The Mascarene Bank Survey was focused on studying the Mascarene Plateau (Indian Ocean) - the geomorphology, benthic habitats and benthos, map the occurrence of fish and crustacean resources. The research team also looked into its oceanographic conditions and recorded the occurrence of microplastics and marine debris. The second leg was carried out to explore the distribution of mesopelagic fish vertically and horizontally, from the higher-oxygen regions of the southern Indian Ocean to the low-oxygen regions of the northern Indian Ocean. This survey studied the effect of the biogeochemical water properties on the distribution of mesopelagic fish and monitored long-term changes in biogeochemistry since WOCE observations from 1995.

³ <http://www.fao.org/in-action/eaf-nansen/surveys/en/>

1.4 Cabo Verde Archipelago

The following is based primarily on Stobberup (2015) unless otherwise stated.

Table 1 shows that there have been various surveys carried out in the Cabo Verde Archipelago, covering a wide range of objectives. Sampling methodology and gears have varied considerably over time. Although these surveys are a source of valuable information, the available data is fragmentary and not consistent over time. Earlier surveys tended to be exploratory in nature, providing qualitative data, whereas the more recent surveys are quantitative, including objectives such as determining the biomass of important pelagic and demersal fish species. In relation to demersal trawl surveys, one should consider differences in gear and vessel characteristics as well as sampling procedures and intensity when comparing with more recent surveys.

Table 1. List of surveys undertaken in Cape Verde waters, indicating the survey objective and gear used. (Source: Stobberup 2015)

Research Vessel	Year	Objective	Method
Walter Herwig	1964	Exploratory survey: fishery resources	Pelagic and bottom trawls
Ernst Haeckel	1976	Exploratory survey: demersal fish	Bottom trawl
Dr. Fridtjof Nansen	1981	Exploratory survey: fishery resources	Acoustics, pelagic and bottom trawls
Playa de Tamaris	1982	Exploratory survey: large pelagics	Longline
Fengur	1984 1985	Demersal fish survey	Bottom trawl and handline
Fengur	1988	Demersal fish survey	Bottom trawl
Islândia	1994	Demersal fish survey	Bottom trawl
Islândia	1994 1995 1996 1997	Commercial fishing: demersal fish	Bottom trawl
Islândia	1995 1996 1997	Exploratory survey: small-scale resources	Handline
Islândia	1997	Exploratory survey: tuna	Longline
Capricórnio	1997	Acoustic survey: small pelagics	Acoustics
Arquipélago	2000	Deep-water resources	Deep longline
Dr. Fridtjof Nansen	2011 ⁴	Ecosystem survey	Acoustics, pelagic and bottom trawls

Small pelagic resources

Two acoustic surveys have been undertaken to determine the biomass of small pelagics, the mackerel scad (*Decapterus macarellus*) in particular. The RV Dr. Fridtjof Nansen undertook the first acoustic assessment in 1981 and the Portuguese RV Capricórnio did the same in 1997 (Table 1). Most of the biomass was concentrated in the narrow shelf areas around the islands, with the more extensive shelf off Boavista accounting for about ¾ of the total fish biomass. Both vessels were relatively large and had difficulties in prospecting because of the narrow shelves around the islands. Progress in technology and data analysis over the period may be part of the explanation for this large difference (decrease) in acoustic estimates.

⁴ Source: IMAR, Cabo Verde

Demersal fish resources

The first survey using a bottom trawl was undertaken in 1964 with only 6 stations sampled. Since then, bottom trawl surveys have taken place sporadically and they have varied in terms of objectives as well as sampling gear and methodology. For example, the 1964 historic survey in Cape Verde was a detour, the main objective being a survey of the Gulf of Guinea area, and the 1976 survey was in fact exploratory in nature. All the surveys included sampling stations in the Boavista-Maio shelf, but sampling of the north western islands (S. Vicente and S. Antão) and southern islands (Santiago, Fogo, Brava) was occasional. This is related to the fact that bottom trawl surveys are difficult in Cape Verde due to the very narrow shelves and difficult bottom conditions, except for a limited area south of Boavista Island. The RV Dr. Fridtjof Nansen survey in 1981 covered most of the archipelago, but the more recent surveys in 1984, 1985, 1988, and 1994 had more intensive sampling.

The Cabo Verde Ecosystem

As mentioned above on the Nansen Programme, the scope was made much broader in 2006 to consider ecosystem considerations. In this context, an Ecosystem Survey off Cape Verde was carried out from 4–18 June 2011 by RV Fridtjof Nansen in collaboration with the government of Cape Verde and the Canary Current Large Marine Ecosystem Project. The objectives were to study pelagic and demersal fish resources and the marine ecosystem, and to establish the physical, chemical and biological characteristics of the ecosystem associated with shelf region of Cabo Verde (FAO, 2011).

National time series of monthly sampling of fish landings (1984-2015) and of biological sampling, including length frequency distributions of 7 commercial species (2004-2020), which should provide data suitable for application of DLM are also available. A summary of Cape Verde national fisheries and oceanographic surveys and sampling programmes is provided in Annex 1.

1.5 Surveys of small pelagics in Northwest Africa

The main series of surveys used in the past in the assessments of the subregion were carried out by the RV Dr. Fridtjof Nansen from 1995 to 2006 (acoustic surveys), during the month of October-December of each year, which were complemented by the RVs Al-Amir Moulay Abdellah (Morocco), Al-Awam (Mauritania), and Itaf Deme (Senegal) in 2007 and 2008 to cover the region (FAO 2018a).

From 2009 to 2011, the surveys were coordinated between RVs of Morocco and Mauritania without the participation of the RV Itaf Deme of Senegal, and attempts have been made to continue the series.

Since 2011, regional coordination of surveys to cover small pelagic stocks appears to have been difficult due to financial and technical reasons. Morocco continued its annual surveys regularly, Mauritania continued its national programmes (Annex 3), and Senegal carried out one acoustic survey in 2015

(Annex 4, Figure 5). The RV Fridtjof Nansen has continued to carry out surveys targeting small pelagic fishes along the Northwest African region (Annex 6) (Source: CECAF 2018).

Figure 5. Example of pelagic surveys carried out in Senegal, indicating acoustic transects and pelagic trawl sampling stations. (a) Map of the study area (Senegambia) and plot of the fishing operations from three vessels: RV Dr Fridtjof Nansen (DFN), RV Itaf Deme (ID) and Diassanga. The zoom shows the localisation of Bamboung and Sangako in Saloum delta (adapted from Sadio and Ecoutin (2013)) where the Diassanga led its inshore fishing operations. Acoustic sampling design in parallel transects (DFN and ID) is overlaid in grey line. The isobath lines are shown in red (500 m), blue (100 m), green (500 m) and purple (30 m). (b) Map of the geographical distribution of *Ethmalosa fimbriata*, *Sardinella aurita*, *Sardinella maderensis*, and *Ilisha africana* sampled from scientific trawl survey (1981-2006). The total surveyed area [10-500 m] is 5600 NM² vs. 1700 NM² [0-10 m] not surveyed (shallow part along the coast, in blue). (Source: Sarre et al. 2018)

The Nansen Programme has continued support in Northwest African region with focused surveys on small pelagics and broader ecosystem surveys. This included (FAO, 2021):

Survey # 2017: Pelagic Stocks and Ecosystem Survey - Leg 1

- Period: 08/05/2017 - 18/07/2017 (66 days)
- Countries: Mauritania - Morocco - Senegal
- Objectives of the Surveys:
- This survey (including four legs 1.1-1.4) addressed abundance and distribution of pelagic resources, environmental conditions within which they were found, and aspects of their early life history. The survey also offered an opportunity to sample and tackle other research topics of high regional and international interest.

Survey # 2019: Pelagic stocks and ecosystems Senegal – Morocco - Leg 4

- Period: 26/09/2019 - 19/12/2019 (74 days)
- Countries:
- Mauritania - Morocco - Senegal
- Objectives of the Surveys:
- This survey (including four legs 4.1-4.4) was conducted to provide a synoptic coverage of the main pelagic resources off Northwest Africa and of the oceanographic conditions in the area and update the historic time series.

Within the framework of a new task in WP2 involving the study of the influence of environmental variability on Northwest Africa small pelagics, time series of biological and environmental data were compiled in FarFish D2.10 (Khalil *et al.*, 2020). The available survey is summarised in Annex 5.

1.6 Demersal surveys in Northwest Africa

The following is based primarily on FAO (2018b), updated with other references, which gives an overview of demersal surveys carried out in Northwest Africa.

Mauritania

In Mauritania, the scientific surveys at sea were initiated by IMROP in the 1980s (Annex 2). These surveys aimed to make an exhaustive inventory of all the available fishery resources, to monitor and collect information on their abundance, collect data on their biological and ecological characteristics and to study the marine environment, etc.

Demersal surveys were initiated by IMROP using the RV N'Diogo between 1982 and 1997, and then using the RV Al Awam. Two surveys were conducted a year: one in the cold season and another in the warm seasons. There are two major categories of surveys:

The demersal surveys (which targets fish, crustaceans, molluscs, etc.) of the continental shelf and slope; and

The Octopus surveys for the study of octopus dynamics in radial zones in areas of abundance.

During the period 2007–2016, the frequency of the octopus surveys was increased to 12 annual surveys, one per month.

During the period 2013–2016, six demersal resource assessment surveys were conducted over the continental shelf and slope at depths of below 6 000 m during the major cold and warm seasons.

Spain carried out three surveys in Mauritania between 2007 and 2009 with the RV VIZCONDE DE EZA. The 2007 survey covered waters of a depth between 400 and 2 000 m, whereas the 2008 and 2009 surveyed part of the continental shelf, thus covering depths of between 80 and 2 000 m. These surveys aimed at mapping the distribution, abundance and biodiversity of demersal fish, cephalopod and shrimp. Bathymetric maps were also drawn using a multi-faceted acoustic sonde. Samples of megabenthos were collected, particularly during the 2009 survey, using different types of gear. This last survey was multidisciplinary: fish yields were obtained with a bottom trawl (Lofoten type), information on hydrology, composition and ichthyoplankton abundance was collected over the entire area. (FAO 2016).

Morocco

In Morocco, for 2013–2016, scientific surveys and monitoring of demersal resources were carried out by the RV Charif Al Idrissi until June 2015 when a technical problem with the vessel led to the RV El Al Hassani taking over for the remainder of 2015, and then the RV Al Amir My Abdellah continuing the surveys from 2016.

Three types of surveys were carried out: assessment surveys to monitor the stock status of cephalopods and associated fish; monitoring surveys for octopus breeding and recruitment in the spring and autumn, respectively; and deep-sea exploratory surveys.

Senegal

Since the 1980s, various demersal surveys have been carried out to provide a fishery-independent measure of fish distribution and abundance of all the species that can be sampled by bottom trawl. The study Ba *et al.* (2018) compiled data from 25 surveys, covering the whole continental shelf, from 10-200m depth. This covers the period from 1986 to 2008 (with five missing years; 1996, 2000, 2002, 2006 and 2007), and gather 2633 hauls. Most of these surveys were carried out by the RV Itaf Deme, complemented by a few surveys carried out by the RV Fridtjof Nansen (Annex 6). It should be noted that these vessels carried out both pelagic and demersal surveys.

2 Observer programmes

FarFish [Deliverable 2.4](#) on ‘Templates and Protocols for Self-sampling’ provided an overview of data collection with a focus on EU fisheries in external waters, thus providing context on possible benefits of implementing self-sampling to cover particular fisheries and/or data types from a cost-effective point of view.

One aspect covered in the above report was observer programmes in place to cover the activity of various EU fisheries in external waters. The focus was primarily on tuna observer programmes, although an overview was given on other fisheries in different contexts.

Access to information (not the data itself) on the EU observer programmes proved difficult, with the IEO being one of the major players. The main reason for this was that a major study was underway on evaluating the observer programmes of EU fisheries in Northwest Africa with a focus on the mixed fisheries agreements (i.e. demersals and small pelagics). However, this study has now been concluded and some key findings are presented in García-Isarch *et al.* (2020). The study objectives were (for the period 2014-2018):

- a) to scrutinise and deeply analyse the available information in DG MARE and MS in order to maximise its use;
- b) to critically analyse the content of these reports to identify strengths and weaknesses in data coverage, with a view to establish a standardised manual for the use of the observers.

For the sake of context, it is important to note that the protocols for mixed Sustainable Fisheries Partnership Agreements (SFPAs) in West Africa (Morocco, Mauritania, Senegal and Guinea-Bissau) include provisions for observers from these countries to join EU vessels. Member States (MS) must also provide biological information from the exploited resources, under the EU Multi-Annual Programme (EU MAP) for the Data Collection Framework (DCF).

EU vessels that land their catches from external waters in the EU, the various MS must have in place a data collection system in place (port sampling or data collection at auctions). However, for vessels that operate and unload their catches outside EU waters, this information can only be obtained from scientific observers and logbooks.

Although the SFPA Protocols establish that observers’ reports should be transmitted to the EU, only a limited number were available at DG MARE. The availability of observers’ reports to the relevant research institutions in both the EU and some CS has been identified by the concerned Joint Scientific Committees (JSCs) of the SFPA as a recurrent problem, resulting in limited information and thus difficulties for the implementation of their work (García- Isarch *et al.* 2020).

A total of 37 reports from SFPAs-observers were provided by DG MARE for analysis (García- Isarch *et al.* 2020). They correspond to 55 observed fishing trips with more than 1,175 days at sea observed, from three EU fleets: black hake trawlers in Senegal⁵, bottom longliners and pelagic trawlers in Morocco⁶. Most of these reports were of very limited utility as the information collected was very basic and thus not very useful for scientific advice purposes. They focused mainly on fishing activity information (vessel and gear characteristics, area, catch, etc) and did not provide any biological information (García- Isarch *et al.* 2020). These study results confirm the findings of FarFish, which indicated that Senegalese observer data (collected on EU vessels) was expected to be of limited use.

Information from 80 DCF-observed fishing trips were available in the concerned EU institutions, containing substantial and detailed information in line with DCF requirements. This corresponded to: 1) Shrimper trawlers operating in Mauritania and Guinea-Bissau; 2) Black hake trawlers in Morocco, Mauritania and Senegal; 3) Cephalopod-finfish trawlers in Guinea-Bissau and 4) Pelagic trawlers in Morocco and Mauritania. A total number of 1,704 fishing days and 7,681 fishing hauls were observed in the 80 fishing trips inventoried, as shown in Table 2 (Garcia-Isarch *et al.* 2020).

Table 2. Summary of fishing trips with DCF observers by type of fleet

FLEET	Fishing trips	Fishing days	Mean duration (days/trip)	No Hauls	Mean No of hauls by trip
Shrimper trawlers	22	971	45	5,250	239
Black hake trawlers	36	272	8	941	26
Cephalopod-finfish trawlers	8	157	20	824	103
Pelagic trawlers	14	273	20	666	48
TOTAL	80	1,704	-	7,681	-

DCF-observer performance on individual vessel trips is considered adequate to meet the DCF requirements for all fleets. However, adequate observer coverage of the fleets was often not achieved, mainly due to the reluctance of some vessel owners to take on observers due to limited space and capacity onboard (García- Isarch *et al.* 2020).

In the case of black hake trawlers, the proportion of trips observed has remained constant, ranging between 6% and 9%, for all the fishing grounds for the period 2016-2018. Over 80% of the observation effort was in Mauritania, which was proportional to the fishing effort. However, this overall coverage

⁵ The numbers of fishing trips observed on board black hake ‘fresh’ trawlers were 24 (2015), 3 (2016) and 1 (2018) together with an unknown number of trips on board one freezer trawler.

⁶ Mauritania does not forward the observer reports automatically and have to be requested. IMROP emphasises the intermittent nature of their observer programmes since their beginning.

masks the fact that there was zero coverage in 2016 and 2018, although it was 25% of fishing trips in 2017.

In contrast to the DCF observer programmes, existing SFPAs observer programmes run by the partner countries usually have an emphasis on compliance (MCS), noting target species, level of bycatch according to categories, fishing area, and gear used. These do not include scientific tasks such as detailed catch data by species and biological sampling, despite these being required by the SFPA-Protocols. Another problem is that there are clear failures on the transmission of the SFPA observer's reports to the EU in spite of the reporting obligations established in the Protocols. García- Isarch *et al.* (2020) had apparent difficulties in accessing the SFPA observer reports, but indicate that the available information does not meet the observer coverage rates and duration established for vessels with different GT and pelagic trawlers in the protocols.

Tuna Fisheries

FarFish [Deliverable 2.4](#) presents an overview of observer programmes with a focus of tuna fisheries, but some general findings are included in the following to provide a more complete overview.

There is an obligation for 5% observer coverage of tuna fishing activity in the context of ICCAT and IOTC, although in the case of the 2-month moratorium on FADs in place in the Atlantic there is an obligation for 100% observer coverage. However, it is important to note that producer organizations representing EU tuna purse seiners, in France (ORTHONGEL) and Spain (ANABAC and OPAGAC), have gone further and developed, in collaboration with

the French Institute for Research for Development (IRD), the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO) and AZTI-Tecnalia (Spain), a Voluntary Observing Programme to ensure 100% coverage of fishing activities through on-board observers and electronic means of surveillance.

In the case of the Indian Ocean, it is actually the Seychelles Fishing Authority that deploys observers on several purse seine fleets, including the Seychelles purse seine fleet. In 2015 for example, a total of 84 deployments were completed on Seychelles purse seiners, covering a total of 3,541 observed days (84% coverage). SFA also provided observer services to other purse seine fleet, the Spanish fleet in particular (Table 3).

Table 3. Observer deployments for 2015. (Source: SFA)

Country	No. of trips observed	No. of days observed
France	17	1028
South Korea	8	324
Mauritius	1	70
Seychelles	84	3541
Spain	120	5277

There has been very limited interest by EU longliners in taking advantage of fishing opportunities provided in the Seychelles SFPAs. On the other hand, Cabo Verde is an important base for tuna fishing operations, the EU longline fleets in particular. However, Cabo Verde does not have a functioning observer programme, which implies that the observers are being deployed by the flag States (Portugal and Spain).

In the case of longliners, it is the Portuguese Institute for the Ocean and Atmosphere (IPMA) and the Spanish Institute of Oceanography (IEO) that are responsible for running scientific observer programmes to cover their respective longline fleets operating in the ICCAT and IOTC Convention areas.

Although flag States have an obligation for 5% observer coverage of their longline fleets, this is achieved in only specific cases. This is linked to the operations of these vessels, which fish in remote areas and pay rare visits to ports, making it difficult and costly to send observers on-board. Some fleets achieve good levels of coverage (e.g. Portugal has achieved an average of 9% in the Indian Ocean), the average level fluctuates about 1-3% (FarFish Deliverable 2.4). In the Atlantic, observer coverage is about 1% of the fishing days in the North Atlantic, and 3% in the South Atlantic (Espino *et al.* 2016).

3 Tuna-RFMOs

This section on tuna-related data has been included on available data of relevance to EU external fisheries for the sake of completeness, although this has been described and used in several FarFish reports. The intention is to give a general overview in the context of available data and situate the differences in approaches used for assessment and management.

Compared to demersal and/or small pelagic resources, tuna stock assessments do not rely on surveys as a main source of information on the abundance and distribution of the resources. This is simply because it is not feasible, within reasonable cost and capacity, to be able to cover the vast expanses of their habitats and fishing grounds using surveys. For tuna, the stock assessments rely on good quality data on catch and effort, including granular (geographical) data on the distribution of these catches. In simplified terms, the more advanced models used incorporate these data coupled with movement data (from tagging studies) and biological data (growth models).

One of the key responsibilities of tuna-RFMOs is to compile these data and to improve data quality as much as possible, considering the many Members and the diversity of fisheries (countries, fleets, gears, fishing grounds, etc.). Within this framework, there are normally better conditions for securing the needed capacity (human and financial) to secure the best available expertise to carry out the modelling work and provide sound scientific advice, albeit there will always be uncertainty attached to the modelling results. And securing good quality data is a constant struggle demanding constant attention and financial means.

Another aspect concerns fisheries governance which is outside the scope of this report, but it is important to bear in mind that a regional fishery body (RFB) with management competences, e.g. tuna-RFMOs as opposed to CECAF which is an advisory body, has more influence and leverage over its members in complying with obligations, including providing data.

Both ICCAT and IOTC (as well as other tuna-RFMOs) compile and maintain various databases on relevant information which is largely publicly available through their websites⁷. It should be noted that the data is provided on a flag state basis, supplied by both contracting and non-contracting (cooperating) parties fishing for tunas. These statistical data are under constant review, taking into account updates and constant efforts to improve data quality.

Table 4. Example of data published by IOTC Secretariat. (Source: IOTC)

Description	Reference period	Last updated	Download dataset
Nominal catch by species and gear, by vessel flag reporting country**	1950-2018	08-04-2020	data file
Catch-and-effort by month, species and gear, by vessel flag reporting country			
CE surface fisheries	1950-2018	18-09-2019	data file
CE longline	1950-2018	18-09-2019	data file
CE other gears	1950-2018	18-09-2019	data file
All CE files	1950-2018	18-09-2019	data file
CE reference	1950-2018	18-09-2019	reference file
Length frequency data			
Tropical tunas	Varies according to species	consult dedicated page	
Temperate tunas		consult dedicated page	
Billfish		consult dedicated page	
Neritic tunas		consult dedicated page	
Sharks and other bycatch species		consult dedicated page	
Fishing craft statistics: number of vessels by country flag, by size category	1950-2016	25-09-2017	Online Data Querying

Additional data or detail are also provided when these are available, such as:

⁷ <https://www.iccat.int/en/accesingdb.html> & <https://www.iotc.org/data-and-statistics>

- List of authorised vessels including their statistics (see also CLAV for a consolidated record across t-RFMOs⁸)
- Catch and effort (CE) data is provided with a maximum spatial aggregation of 1°x1° grid area for purse seine and 5°x5° grid area for longline. Note however that not all CE data is available with this resolution (e.g. not for most artisanal fleets, etc.)
- Bycatch & discard data including tuna species, as well as sharks, seabirds, marine turtles, marine mammals, and other marine species.
- Biological data such as individual lengths or weights of tuna species and sharks, LW equations, maturity/fecundity data, growth equations, various weight conversion equations.
- Tagging data (TD) is also available and the tuna-RFMO Secretariat can be contacted for more information about the data that are available, and procedures required to obtain this information.

As a general rule when providing catch and catch-related data, it should not be possible to identify an individual vessel within a time/area stratum. In cases when an individual vessel can be identified, the data are aggregated by time, area or flag to preclude such identification, before placing this in the public domain.

⁸ <http://clav.iotc.org/>

2 Conclusions and discussion

FarFish WP2 (Advancing biological knowledge and evaluation of current stock assessment models) aimed to collect and collate data for input to feed models and management tools that will provide better understanding of the biology and ecology of the respective species and ecosystems, and would be used by other WPs (1, 3, 4, 5 & 6) for stakeholder interaction, development of management recommendations (MRs), modelling, stock assessment and for visualisation tools. Data for the FFDB for application of DLMs and visualization were of particular importance.

This document is the third and final deliverable on the FFDB. As noted in the introduction, it was possible to obtain sufficient data for the needs of the other WPs, especially for the FarFish-DLMtool developed and implemented in WP6. However, it was not possible to obtain data from many relevant sources, namely national survey and Nansen survey data. As outlined in the Memo in Annex 7, numerous attempts were made to obtain Nansen survey data for the different CS, but due to convoluted bureaucratic processes, it was not possible to obtain any Nansen survey data. While not all Nansen survey data is suitable or adequate for FarFish purposes, due to limitations in terms of survey design, frequency and coverage, there are certainly series of surveys that would provide data that could have been useful. We strongly endorse the recommendations of Dr. Erik Olsen in the memo (Annex 7) for *“the need for an urgent revision of the Data Policy to make it more open and transparent, allow automatic access to data older than five years as well as meta-data, and importantly to reduce bureaucracy and complexity when applying for access to data still under limited access criteria”*. Furthermore, we suggest that improvements be made in the strategic planning and survey design so that useful time series of data can be obtained for different regions, that can be used for stock assessment, application of EAF and monitoring global changes.

As shown in this document, with the exception of the Seychelles CS for which the requested information was not provided, there is a wealth of data available in the form of national research surveys for small pelagics, demersal species, supplemented by environmental data. Such data can certainly be used for analysis of trends, calculation of indicators, implementing DLM, and for management. Indeed, there are several examples from the past of the use of research survey data from the CS by FarFish participants to carry out stock assessments or analysis of trends and indicators (Kerzini et al. (2005).

In conclusion, we highly recommend that full use is made of national research survey data in the context of DLM approaches for stock assessment, for multi-species and trophic modelling, and for monitoring of global changes.

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Annexes

Annex 1. Fisheries and oceanographic surveys from Cape Verde. (Source: INDP)

Year	Month	Type of survey / sampling	Data
1984-2015	all	Commercial fishing	Fish landings
2004-2020	all	Sampling of landings of 7 commercial species	Biological sampling and length frequency
2014	July - September	Pink lobster (<i>Palinurus charlestoni</i>) experimental fishing	Fishing and biological sampling
2010, 2011, 2012	-	Experimental fishing	Biomass estimation of striped Soldier shrimp <i>Plesionika edwardsii</i>
2003, 2005		Fishing surveys	Species composition
2001	April	Deep demersal prospection (report)	Species composition, temperature, CPUE, new species occurrence
1997	July - August	Oceanographic and biomass	Environmental parameters, ictioplankton abundance, acoustic
1994		Demersal trawl	Environmental parameters, catch data, abundance, Species composition

Annex 2. Demersal surveys carried out in Mauritania for the estimation of abundance, biomass, species composition, size distributions, and environmental parameters. (Source: IMROP)

Year	Survey code	Month	Type	Focus
1982	AL8211D	11	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1982	ND8201D	1	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1982	ND8205D	5	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1982	ND8207D	7	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1983	AL8301D	1	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1983	ND8301D	1	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1983	ND8303D	3	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1983	ND8308D	8	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1983	ND8310D	10	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1984	AL8301D	1	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1984	AL8408D	8	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1984	AL8412G	12	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1984	ND8403D	3	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1985	AL8412G	12	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1985	AL8503D	3	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1985	AL8508D	8	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1985	AL8512D	12	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1986	AL8602D	2	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1986	AL8605D	5	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1986	AL8608D	8	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1986	ND8609D	9	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1986	ND8610T	10	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1986	ND8611C	11	Demersal trawl	Demersals
1987	ND8307T	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1987	ND8701C	1	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1987	ND8703D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1987	ND8703T	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1987	ND8705C	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1987	ND8706C	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1987	ND8709C	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1987	ND8709D	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1987	ND8712C	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1988	ND8803D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1988	ND8805C	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1988	ND8806D	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1988	ND8808C	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1988	ND8809D	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1989	ND8903D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1989	ND8904D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1989	ND8906D	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus

Year	Survey code	Month	Type	Focus
1989	ND8908D	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1989	ND8909D	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1989	ND8912D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1990	ND9003D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1991	ND9103D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1991	ND9108D	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1991	ND9108M	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1992	ND9206D	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9305C	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9306C	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9307C	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9307D	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9308C	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9309C	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9310C	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9311C	11	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9312C	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1993	ND9312D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9401C	1	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9402C	2	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9403C	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9403D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9404C	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9405C	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9406C	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9406D	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9407C	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9408C	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9409C	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9409D	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9410C	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9411C	11	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1994	ND9412C	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1995	ND9501C	1	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1995	ND9502C	2	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1995	ND9503C	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1995	ND9504C	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1995	ND9506D	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1995	ND9509A	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1995	ND9511A	11	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1996	ND9601D	1	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1996	ND9605D	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus

Year	Survey code	Month	Type	Focus
1996	ND9609A	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1996	ND9610A	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1996	ND9612D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1997	AW9710A	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1997	AW9710D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1998	AW9804D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1998	AW9807D	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1998	AW9808A	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1998	AW9810A	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1998	AW9810D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1998	AW9812D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1999	AW9812D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1999	AW9904D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1999	AW9906D	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1999	AW9909A	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1999	AW9910D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
1999	AW9912D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AM0005D	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AM0005M	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AM0010D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AW0003D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AW0005M	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AW0007D	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AW0008A	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AW0009D	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AW0010A	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AW0011D	11	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2000	AW9912D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2001	AM0105D	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2001	AM0110D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2001	AW0104D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2001	AW0108A	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2001	AW0109D	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2001	AW0110A	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2001	AW0112d	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2002	AM0207D	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2002	AM0210D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2002	AW0112d	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2002	AW0203d	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2002	AW0209A	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2002	AW0210A	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2002	AW0212D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus

Year	Survey code	Month	Type	Focus
2003	AW0212D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2003	AW0304D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2003	aw0306DT	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2003	AW0308A	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2004	AM0402D	2	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2004	AW0402D	2	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2004	AW0408A	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2004	AW0408DC	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2004	AW0410A	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2004	AW0410D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2005	AM0504D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2005	AW0504A	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2005	AW0504C	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2005	AW0505A	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2005	AW0505D	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2005	AW0510A	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2005	AW0512D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2006	AM0610HD	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2006	AW0604D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2006	AW0608A	8	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2006	AW0610A	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2007	AM0701Mul	1	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2007	AM0702MUL	2	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2007	AM0704Mul	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2007	AW0707D	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2007	AW0709A	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2007	AW0709D	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2007	AW0711A	11	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2008	AW0803J	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2008	AW0804A	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2008	AW0804D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2008	AW0806A	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2008	AW0809A	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2008	AW0810D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2008	AW0811A	11	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2009	AW0909A	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2009	AW0911A	11	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2009	AW0912D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2010	AW0912D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2010	AW1004D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2010	AW1007A	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2010	AW1010D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus

Year	Survey code	Month	Type	Focus
2010	AW1012A	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2011	AW1105D	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2011	AW1107A	7	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2011	AW1109D	9	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2012	AW1203D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2014	AW1405D	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2014	AW1410D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2015	AM1505D	5	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2015	AW1503D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2016	AW1604D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2016	AW1612D	12	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2016	AW1910D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2017	AW1706D	6	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2017	AW1711D	11	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2018	AW1804D	4	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2018	AW1810D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2019	AW1903D	3	Demersal trawl	Octopus
2019	AW1910D	10	Demersal trawl	Octopus

Annex 3. Pelagic surveys (acoustic & pelagic trawl) carried out in Mauritania for the estimation of abundance, biomass, species composition, size distributions, and environmental parameters. (Source: IMROP)

Year	Vessel	Survey code	Month	Type *
1995	Atlantida	ATAC0795	7	pelagic trawl
1997	Atlantida	ATAC0797	7	pelagic trawl
1998	Atlantida	ATAC0798	7	pelagic trawl
1999	Atlantida	ATAC0799	7	pelagic trawl
2000	Atlantida	ATAC0700	7	pelagic trawl
2001	Atlantida	ATAC0701	7	pelagic trawl
2003	Atlantniro	ATRE1203	12	pelagic trawl
2004	Atlantida	ATAC0704	7	pelagic trawl
2005	Atlantniro	ATRE1205	12	pelagic trawl
2006	Atlantida	ATAC0706	7	pelagic trawl
2006	Atlantniro	ATRE1206	12	pelagic trawl
2007	Atlantida	ATAC0707	7	pelagic trawl
2007	Atlantniro	ATRE1207	12	pelagic trawl
2008	Atlantida	ATAC0708	7	pelagic trawl
2009	Atlantida	ATAC0709	7	pelagic trawl
2009	Atlantniro	ATRE1209	12	pelagic trawl
2010	Atlantida	ATAC0710	7	pelagic trawl
2010	Atlantniro	ATRE1210	12	pelagic trawl
2011	Atlantida	ATAC0711	7	pelagic trawl
2012	Atlantniro	ATRE1212	12	pelagic trawl
1995	F.Nansen	FNAC1195	11	pelagic trawl
1996	F.Nansen	FNAC1196	11	pelagic trawl
1997	F.Nansen	FNAC1197	11	pelagic trawl
1998	F.Nansen	FNAC1198	11	pelagic trawl
1999	F.Nansen	FNAC1199	11	pelagic trawl
2000	F.Nansen	FNAC1100	11	pelagic trawl
2001	F.Nansen	FNAC1101	11	pelagic trawl
2001	F.Nansen	FNAC0601	6	pelagic trawl
2002	F.Nansen	FNAC1102	11	pelagic trawl
2002	F.Nansen	FNAC0602	6	pelagic trawl
2003	F.Nansen	FNAC1103	11	pelagic trawl
2003	F.Nansen	FNAC0603	6	pelagic trawl
2004	F.Nansen	FNAC1104	11	pelagic trawl
2005	F.Nansen	FNAC1105	11	pelagic trawl
2006	F.Nansen	FNAC1106	11	pelagic trawl
2015	F.Nansen	FNAC1115	11	pelagic trawl
2017	F.Nansen	FNAC0617	6	pelagic trawl
2019	F.Nansen	FNAC1119	11	pelagic trawl
2003	AlAwam	AWAC0303	3	pelagic trawl

Year	Vessel	Survey code	Month	Type *
2003	AlAwam	AWAC0703	7	pelagic trawl
2003	AlAwam	AWAC1103	11	pelagic trawl
2004	AlAwam	AWAC0304	3	pelagic trawl
2004	AlAwam	AWAC1104	11	pelagic trawl
2005	AlAwam	AWAC0305	3	pelagic trawl
2005	AlAwam	AWAC1105	11	pelagic trawl
2006	AlAwam	AWAC0306	3	pelagic trawl
2007	AlAwam	AWAC1107	11	pelagic trawl
2008	AlAwam	AWAC0308	3	pelagic trawl
2008	AlAwam	AWAC1108	11	pelagic trawl
2009	AlAwam	AWAC0309	3	pelagic trawl
2009	AlAwam	AWAC0709	7	pelagic trawl
2009	AlAwam	AWAC1109	11	pelagic trawl
2010	AlAwam	AWAC0710	7	pelagic trawl
2010	AlAwam	AWAC1110	11	pelagic trawl
2012	AlAwam	AWAC0712	7	pelagic trawl
2014	AlAwam	AWAC1114	11	pelagic trawl
2015	AlAwam	AWAC0715	7	pelagic trawl
2018	AlAwam	AWAC0318	3	pelagic trawl
2018	AlAwam	AWAC0718	7	pelagic trawl
2019	AlAwam	AWAC0718	7	pelagic trawl

Annex 4. Artisanal fishery, coastal and deep-water trawl, small pelagics and environmental surveys from Senegal. (Source: CRODT)

Year	Month	Type	Data
1974 to 2019	All months	Artisanal Fisheries	catch, effort, species composition, size distributions
1977 to 2001	All months	Programme PPC (coastal small pelagics)	catch, effort, species composition, size distributions
1977 to 2019	All months	Economic	prices of the main species landed by the artisanal fishery
1982 to 2019	Season, warm and cold	Survey of small vessels	quantification of artisanal fishing units
1952 to 2002	All months	Coastal environmental stations	environmental parameters
1986 to 1988	Season, warm and cold	Environmental surveys	environmental parameters
1983 to 2006	All months	Foreign deep-water demersal industrial trawlers	catch, effort, species composition
1992 to 2006	All months	Foreign industrial coastal demersal trawlers	catch, effort, species composition
1971 to 2019	All months	National industrial coastal and deep-water demersal	catch, effort, species composition
1966 to 2017	All months	Port de Dakar sardine fleet	catch, effort, species composition
1986 to 2016	Season, warm and cold	Deepwater demersal survey	global and species biomasses, abundance indices, biology, etc. (some gaps)
1986 to 2016	Season, warm and cold	Coastal demersal survey	global and species biomasses, abundance indices, biology, etc. (some gaps)
1986 to 2015	Season, warm and cold	Acoustic survey (pelagics)	global and species biomasses, abundance indices, biology, etc. (some gaps)

Annex 5. Small pelagics surveys from Morocco. (Source: FarFish D2.10)

Year	Months	Type of survey/sampling	Data collected
1990-2017	yearly data	Artisanal and coastal fisheries	Catch, fishing effort, species composition, length composition, age composition, CPUE, weight, growth parameters
1950-2014	yearly data	Industrial fisheries (National and International)	Catch by gear type (reported and unreported data) -Landing and discards-, Species composition
1950-2014	yearly data	Artisanal fishery	Catch by gear type (reported and unreported data)-Landing and discards, Species composition
1950-2014	yearly data	Subsistence fishery	Catch by gear type (reported and unreported data)-Landing and discards, Species composition
1950-2014	yearly data	Recreational fishery	Catch by gear type (reported and unreported data)-Landing and discards, Species composition
1950-2014	yearly data	Artisanal and Industrial fisheries	Landed value (in million US\$)
1970-2016	yearly data	Marine aquaculture practices (CECAF capture production)	Catch data
2006-2017	June, November, December	National acoustic campaigns (by the RV Al Amir Moulay Abdellah)	Acoustic biomass indices
1990-2017	yearly data	Official statistics of DPM, ONP and INRH	Catch and fishing effort (as graphs), and biological parameters
2006-2017	September to November	National acoustic campaigns (by the RV Al Amir Moulay Abdellah)	Biomass estimated
1995-2017	September, June and July	Acoustic survey by RV Atlantniro	Biomass estimated (table (for just anchovy) and as a graphs for others species)

Annex 6. Overview of the surveys used, vessels involved (DFN: RV Dr Fridtjof Nansen, ID: RV Itaf Deme, DS: Diassanga shallow water boat, surveying periods and data available. NASC: Nautical area scattering coefficient (m² NM⁻²), for sardinella group (SARD = *Sardinella aurita* and *Sardinella maderensis*), horse mackerels group (HORS = *Trachurus trecae* and *Caranx rhonchus*), other clupeids group (i.e. “P1”: including *Ethmalosa fimbriata* and *Ilisha africana*) other pelagic fish group (i.e. “P2”: other than clupeids and HORS). (Source: Sarre et al. 2018)

Vessels	Period	Country/Area	Data available	Interest
DFN	Nov 2005 Nov 2006	Senegal and The Gambia	Pooled NASC data [20–500 m] of SARD, HORS, P1 and P2	NASC distribution of both sardinella pooled Clupeid species occurrence in trawls, position and depth
	Nov 1981 to Nov 2004	Senegal and The Gambia	Pooled NASC data [20–500 m] of SARD, HORS, P1 and P2	Clupeid species occurrence in trawls, position and depth
ID	Nov 2004 Nov 2005 Nov 2007	Senegal and The Gambia	ID as DFN but with separated NASC [10–500 m] for <i>S. aurita</i> and <i>S. maderensis</i>	NASC distribution of <i>S. aurita</i> and <i>S. maderensis</i>
	Mar 2003 Mar 2004 May 2005 Nov 2006	Only Senegal	Idem as DFN with separated NASC for <i>S. aurita</i> and <i>S. maderensis</i>	Clupeid species occurrence per bottom depth from trawls
	2008 2009 2010 2011	Delta Saloum	Relative biomass per species (64 species among which <i>E. fimbriata</i> , <i>S. maderensis</i> , <i>S. aurita</i> and <i>I. africana</i>)	Clupeid species occurrence, position and depth

Annex 7.

Memo:

EAF Nansen data for the EU FarFish project

By: Dr. Erik Olsen, Head of Research – Marine Research in Developing Countries, Institute of Marine Research, Norway

March 25th, 2021

The EU project FarFish (<https://www.farfish.eu/>) started in 2017, and since then has been attempting to access data from surveys collected as part of the FAO EAF Nansen programme with the RV *Dr. Fridtjof Nansen* in Senegal, Cabo Verde, Mauritania and Seychelles. Partners within the FarFish consortium, including IMROP, CRODT, INDP/IMAR and SFA have requested approval from their authorities that EAF Nansen data from their countries be used in the FarFish project. These approvals were confirmed by Senegal, Mauritania, and Seychelles in 2019. However, the project has been unsuccessful in gaining access to the data, thereby limiting the planned data analysis for these regions.

During the project planning, both IMR and FAO were invited to become project partners, in large part to facilitate access to EAF Nansen data. IMR accepted the invitation, but FAO declined. Upon the start of the project, a process for gaining access to EAF Nansen data from FarFish partner countries started. The first attempt was made directly through IMR, who are custodians of the EAF Nansen data. The FarFish consortium was informed that IMR is, however, not at liberty to share EAF Nansen data without approval from the EAF Nansen project. This requires clearance by both the relevant partner countries and the EAF Nansen coordination unit at FAO. In June 2019, the FarFish Coordinator submitted a formal request for access to EAF Nansen data to the partner countries. The formal data requests were followed by correspondence with the EAF Nansen coordination unit at FAO to ensure that the correct protocols and procedures were followed. At this time, the EAF Nansen data policy was under revision and FAO informed the FarFish Coordinator that this would cause some delays in handling the data requests.

By June 2020, several partners had responded positively to the data requests, but not all had supplied official letters by their relevant data owners (e.g. official EAF Nansen partner institutions). Some also responded that data older 5 years were freely available, which was the rule under the old data policy, but is not continued in the revised policy. Others also responded that IMR had full access to the data and could share it, which is contrary to IMR's role as data custodian. Thus, the EAF Nansen coordination unit at FAO never gave clearance for access to the data.

As of 2020 the FarFish project had therefore failed to gain access to the EAF Nansen data. This was due to a combination of lack of formal letters allowing access of data by the official EAF Nansen partner institutions in Senegal, Cabo Verde, Mauritania and Seychelles, delays caused by the revision of the EAF Nansen data policy, and delays by the EAF Nansen coordination unit at FAO in processing and helping with handling the request for data.

By the end of 2020, the FarFish project decided it was too late to process any EAF Nansen data even if access was granted, and the process of trying to get access to the data was terminated.

Conclusions:

In its attempts to guard against “parachute science” where researchers from industrialized nations take data from low-income nations and publish it with little benefit to the data-owners, the EAF Nansen Data Policy has gone to the extreme where even legitimate data-requests from reputable projects like FarFish are effectively stopped due to bureaucratic and convoluted processes.

Furthermore, it is also unfortunate that the revised data policy is even stricter than the old one, barring the open access to data older than five years. The EAF Nansen Data Policy has thus evolved contrary to the current aims and objectives of open science and data sharing that are the foundations for addressing global challenges and achieving the SDGs.

The failure of FarFish to access relevant EAF Nansen data highlights the need for an urgent revision of the Data Policy to make it more open and transparent, allow automatic access to data older than five years as well as meta-data, and importantly to reduce bureaucracy and complexity when applying for access to data still under limited access criteria.

